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Democratisation in Africa: Lessons from the 2022 Kenyan Presidential Election

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Abstract

The principal objective of this paper is to examine conduct of the 2022 Kenya's presidential election. More precisely, it attempts to identify the best practices as lessons for democratization of the entire continent of Africa. The study that culminated in the paper was qualitative in nature, being based on the case study of the presidential election conducted in August 2022 in Kenya. For this end, this paper used observation, expert opinions, and documentary review for getting both primary and secondary data.

The presidential election in Kenya largely met the threshold of a free, fair and credible election. The transparency was lauded by many and the constitutional provisions on timelines and corresponding activities served to boost predictability of events, which contributed to cooling tension and avert post-election violence like witnessed in 2007/8. The election was challenged in the Supreme Court and the hearing was open to the public until determination, that upheld the result. The role of the media and police was highlighted. However, several issues were observed that needs to be fixed to improve participation, voter turnout, voter education, budgetary constraints, resource allocation and communication of results and clarifying issues. Despite the glitches, the Kenyan electoral experience confirms the theory that repetitive

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elections breed democratic values, hence it offers good lessons to African countries.

This paper recommends improvement in independence of the electoral management bodies and commissioners, solidifying election processes in legislation. Others include transparency of the entire process, adequate preparation including testing technologies involved, adequate resources released timely. It also recommends sufficient voter education, involving stakeholders and better communication.

Keywords: *Africa, Kenya, Democratisation, Electoral management Bodies, Elections.*

1. Introduction

The concept of democracy (democratia) from words (demos) “people” and (kratos) “power” or “rule”, meaning ‘rule by the people’, originated in ancient Greece in the 5th century, (Lindell and Scott, 1999). Fundamental principles in a functioning democracy includes ‘democracy’, ‘constitutionalism’ and ‘liberalism’ (Lynch & Crawford, 2011). Democratisation is the transition to a more democratic political regime (Nwogu, 2015). It is influenced by many factors like economic development, education and civil society (Przeworski, et al, 2006).

Democracy requires that each individual be free to participate in the political community’s self-government. This means people are the ultimate authority and the source of power of the government (Mesfin, 2008). To ensure the government protects the welfare, interest and fundamental rights of the electorate, the powers are limited by authoritative fundamental laws called “constitutions”. The constitution defines the powers of the government and therefore limits *what* it does and *how* it does it, in what is referred to as “the rule of law”. This is within the concept of electoral justice, which Orozco-Henriquez *et al* (2010) defined as means and mechanisms for ensuring that each action, procedure and decision related to the electoral process is in line with the law and protecting or restoring the enjoyment of electoral rights, including complaint process.

Elections are understood as periodic and *de jure* participatory, contested, and legitimate institutions used to select representatives to the executive or legislative branches of government (Lindberg, 2006:16). Holding *regular, periodic, free, fair* and *all-inclusive* election remain a key tenet of a democratic political system (Mutua, 2022; Mesfin, 2008; Dahl, Shapiro, Cheibib, 2003). The people should also have access to alternative sources of information and therefore, freedom of press is essential in a democratic government.

Electoral systems determine “the rules according to which the voters may express their political preferences and according to which it is possible to convert votes into parliamentary seats or in government posts” (Dahl, Shapiro, Cheibib, 2003). Therefore, institutes of electoral procedures are a significant part of determining the outcome of an election. Free and fair Elections with continuous political competition between individuals or parties are the critical methods of social control distinguishing democracy from dictatorship (Bratton and Bhoojedhur, 2019).

Africa has witnessed mixed trends in democratisation, with some nations making great strides as others reverse the earlier gains (Mesfin, 2008). Most countries in Africa have independent bodies to oversee these elections, but in most instances, they are marred in irregularities. Most African countries are accused of conduction of coronation exercise instead of conducting credible elections (Mesfin, 2008). This paper aims to explore the conduct of the Kenyan presidential election in 2022 and pick lessons on democratisation in Africa. More precisely, the paper seeks to assess conduct of electoral management body, the voter education, registration, voting process, transmission and announcement of results. It will assess the relevant legislation.

The findings of the paper will inform policy makers and the electoral bodies on how to conduct inclusive, free, fair and credible elections in Africa. It will help shape the election legislation, allocation of resources, independence of the electoral bodies and selection of its commissioners. The paper fills the gap resulting from the lack of empirical evidence regarding the conduct of elections as a means to improving democratisation in Africa. It demonstrates how systematic research on electoral processes could be used to generate evidence that informs and motivates policy and legislative changes. The paper also applies the theory of democratisation - that repetitive elections breed democratic values – and hence show how electoral reforms could be attained.

The paper is organised as follows: the first part addresses the concept of democracy in Africa and trend in democratisation in Africa and Kenya. It will then explore electoral processes in Africa and Kenya. It will thereafter explore the conduct of the presidential election and concludes with recommendations.

Methodology

The study that culminated in the paper was qualitative in nature, being based on the case study of the presidential election conducted in August 2022 in Kenya. For this end, this paper used observation, expert opinions, and documentary review for getting both primary and secondary data. It reviewed the legislation pertaining to the electoral processes in Kenya, including the set-up of electoral management body, selection of commissioners, and the conduct of elections.

Democratization in Africa

Lindberg (2006) observed that whereas there are many views on what democracy is or ought to be, a common denominator among modern democracies is conducting democratic elections. In this context, democracy means self-government by a sovereign people. The same author argued that at least three dimensions are necessary instruments for the realization of self-government: equality of political participation, freedom of political competition, and legitimacy of the idea of self-government. Since Bratton and van de Walle (1997)'s study, little had been studied in African democracy and elections until this Lindberg's study. The larger theoretical argument made in Lindberg (2006)'s study was that repetitive elections, even when flawed, are one of the important causal factors in democratization. It speaks to the resurfacing recognition among scholars that Rustow (1970) had an important point when he argued that democratic behaviour produces democratic values and not the other way around.

Bratton and van de Walle (1997) argued that elections alone are not sufficient to make a democracy, yet no other institution precedes participatory, competitive, and legitimate elections in instrumental importance for self-government. Therefore, by studying the electoral processes—the campaign, polling day, the immediate response to results, the acceptance or rejection of the outcome by various groups—we study the mechanism of translating people's power to rule into governmental power as vested in systems of representative government (Bratton and van de Walle, 1997). This is the focus of this paper, and more so, the participation, competition, and legitimacy—as democratic qualities of elections.

There are many challenges of the democratization process in Africa. One of these challenges is the wide prevalence of military coups. The

Arab Spring¹ and recent trend in coups indicates that there is still a long way to go as gains made in the last two decades are reversed (Adekoya, 2021). McGowan (2003) study indicated that sub-Saharan Africa experienced 80 successful coups and 108 failed coup attempts between 1956 and 2001, an average of four a year. This figure halved in the period from then till 2019 as most African nations turned to democracy (Mwai, 2022), only for it to once again be on the ascendance. Burkina Faso, Mali, Guinea are the recent cases. Notably, the perpetrators do not term the act as a coup. They have varied reasons for the takeover, ranging from corruption, bad governance, and unemployment which is causing desperation.

Another basic challenge is poverty where the number of extremely poor people in sub-Saharan Africa is increasing and now estimated to have crossed the 500 million mark, nearly half the population of the continent (Adekoya, 2021). Africa has the youngest population in the world with a median age of 20 years, with 75% of the population being under the age of 35 (Ausubel, 2022). It is the fastest growing continent, in terms of population, intensifying the pressure on resources (Kazeem, 2022). Persistent conflicts, vagaries of climate change and the Covid-19 pandemic are making this worse. These create fertile conditions for forceful annexation of power and for increasingly desperate young Africans who have lost patience with their corrupt leaders to welcome coupists promising radical change, as was witnessed on the streets of Guinea following the takeover, with some elated Guineans even kissing the soldiers (Adekoya, 2022).

Lack of change of behaviour is also another challenge. Worryingly, research shows that many Africans are increasingly ceasing to believe elections can deliver the leaders they want. Surveys conducted across 19 African countries in 2019/20 showed just 4 in 10 respondents (42%) now believe elections work well to ensure "MPs reflect voters' views" and to "enable voters remove non-performing leaders." (Afrobarometer, 2022). It means less than half believe elections guarantee representativeness and accountability, key ingredients of functional democracies. Afrobarometer (2022) pointed out that it is not that Africans no longer want to choose their leaders via elections, it is simply that many now believe their political systems are far from credible. The continent has witnessed those sitting in power changing the constitutions

¹ Definition available at <<https://www.britannica.com/event/Arab-Spring>>, (accessed 21 September 2022).

to extend their terms when they are no longer eligible to contest, examples being Uganda, Ivory Coast, Rwanda and Guinea (Afrobarometer, 2022). Elections therefore have been little more than springboards for leaders who, once in office, subvert democratic institutions to consolidate their position (Onyulo, 2017; Mesfin, 2008). Part of what motivates them to cling to power include economic and political privileges, and some fear prosecutions from corruption and other crimes or even retribution from persecuted political opponents (Onyulo, 2017).

African countries share a lot in common, when it comes to democratic gains. The Economist Intelligence Unit (EIU) (2023)'s Democracy Index 2022, ranked 167 countries globally, based on five categories: *electoral process and pluralism, functioning of government, political participation, political culture, and civil liberties*. Based on its scores on a range of indicators within these categories, each country is then classified as one of four types of regime: “full democracy”, “flawed democracy”, “hybrid regime” or “authoritarian regime” (EIU, 2023).

Democracy Index 2022, by regime type

	No. of countries	% of countries	% of world population
Full democracies	24	14.4	8.0
Flawed democracies	48	28.7	37.3
Hybrid regimes	36	21.6	17.9
Authoritarian regimes	59	35.3	36.9

Note. “World” population refers to the total population of the 167 countries and territories covered by the Index. Since this excludes only micro states, this is nearly equal to the entire estimated world population.

Source: EIU.

With over a third of the world’s population and countries living under authoritarian regimes, democracy remains a pipe dream for many. The trend for African states shows that it has consistently ranked below the global average. In 2022, the average score was 4.14 when the global average was 5.29. That average score places many African countries under authoritarian regimes. Kenya’s score is 5.05 and is ranked 94th globally and categorised as hybrid regime. Only Mauritius with a score of 8.14 is categorised as a full democracy. Botswana, South Africa and Namibia follows under flawed democracy. This shows that there is still a long way to go, yet the trend is worsening for African countries, on average.

Democratisation in Kenya

Kenya gained internal self-government from Britain on 1 June 1963 and attained political independence on 12 December 1963 and became a Republic on 12 December 1964. The country has, since independence, been under civilian rule, except for an attempted coup on 1 August 1982 that was swiftly put down by the army (Aywa, 2015). With 11 general elections since it obtained political independence, Kenya has a long history of holding elections and using elections as a legitimating tool for governments. Elections in Kenya are repeated after every five years, and a winning presidential candidate is eligible for two terms.

The principles of electoral system in Kenya are set out in Article 81 of the Constitution of Kenya, 2010 (hereinafter, the Constitution). This supports the citizens' political rights as provided for in Article 38, fair representation of persons with disabilities, compliance with the two-thirds gender rule, universal suffrage based on the aspirations of fair representation and equality of the vote and free and fair elections, espoused in sub-article (e).

With a small variation in the presidential system, where a candidate must garner 50% of the valid votes plus 1 and at least 25% of the valid votes cast in each of more than half of the 47 counties², the electoral system in Kenya is dominantly First-Past-The-Post (FPTP) system (simple majority), for single member electoral areas³. Special interest seats proportional representation is applied in party lists in the Senate, the National Assembly and the County Assembly, as provided for under Elections Act.

The 2022 general election in Kenya was the third since the promulgation of the Constitution, and the seventh since the start of multiparty politics, in 1991 (Onyulo, 2022). Historically, Kenyan elections have been polluted by myriad irregularities, with the last five election results being challenged in courts of law. Ethnicity has become a major factor of electoral politics, in part due to the combination of the 'first-past-the-post' electoral system and ethnically designed constituencies (Aywa, 2015). Ethnic tensions have in turn fuelled several cycles of election-related violence. The 2022 elections ushered in the Kenya's fifth president, after Jomo Kenya (1963-1978), Daniel Moi (1978-2002), Mwai Kibaki (2002-2013), and Uhuru Kenyatta (2013-2022).

² The Constitution of Kenya 2010, Article 138.

³ *Ibid.*, Articles 97, 98, 181 and 193. Implied, since, though not explicitly stated, there is no provision for a special majority, as is the case with the election of the President.

Kenyan Politics

The trend since independence shows that Kenyan politics is based on ethnicity and communities mostly vote as a block to particular candidates (Aywa, 2015). Kenya has been ruled by only two communities: Kikuyu and Kalenjin, and this appears to be continuing. Jomo Kenyatta (Kikuyu) ruled from the independence till his death in 1978 and Daniel Moi (Kalenjin) took over and ruled until 2002. Mwai Kibaki (Kikuyu) took over until 2013 when Uhuru Kenya (Kikuyu) took over. William Ruto (Kalenjin) has been declared President-elect, and if he succeeds in his second term in 2027, might rule for another ten years. Raila Odinga (Luo) has attempted to ascend to power five times, and falling short, and all the times rejecting the results alleging rigging. He has however been praised for shaping the democracy in Kenya (Mbaku, 2022).

Even though 2022 campaign was dominated by issues, there were ethnic undertones. This can be seen by the voting patterns, which appears to have followed the traditional way of voting in blocks and tribal kingpins having a big say on who would be voted in. Even though Kikuyu community did not have a leading contender, all the four candidates in this election had Kikuyu running mates, a clear strategy to tap into the vote rich community. Analysis by *The Nation* showed that two-thirds of Ruto's votes came from ten counties in Mount Kenya Region, mostly inhabited by Kikuyu and seven counties in the Rift Valley, mostly inhabited by Kalenjin.

The elections had been reduced to a war of might between communities, with key issues bedevilling the society playing second fiddle. The downside of this is that even candidates marred with integrity issues, still emerged winners in elections since the electorate see first where he comes from rather than the value to them. This could be an example of what Mutua termed as Locke's fraud (Mutua, 2022). The politicians have also taken advantage of the situation and usually play victim, even when the courts have declared them guilty of economic crimes and capital offences.

From a history of ethnic clashes that dominated the 1990s and the post-election crisis of 2007/8 when over 1,000 people were killed and almost 700,000 displaced, it can be said that the country is completely different, going by the conduct of the 2022 election (The Conversation, 2022:13). It can be said that as democracy matures, trust builds given the confidence electorate gain on the election to provide expected outcomes (The Conversation, 2022:13).

Electoral Practices and Trends in Africa

Although elections do not equate with democracy, the holding of free and fair elections is recognized as a hallmark of accountability and a fundamental component of a functioning democracy (Bratton and Bhoojdhur, 2019). This is a link reinforced by the African Union (AU) while setting electoral standards for the continent (AU, 2007).

The right to political participation is the central plank of the basic freedoms guaranteed by international law and liberal constitution (Mutua, 2022:7). Citizens participate directly or indirectly through their representatives in the conduct of government and public affairs. This is exercised fundamentally through the vote – a secret ballot in genuine periodic free and fair elections in universal suffrage for all without any form of discrimination – is a bedrock of democracy (Mutua, 2022:7). However, this is rarely achieved, due to populace’s inability to make informed choices. Their wishes are swayed by political cartels, who appeal to their greed and gullibility, and also the laws, norms, structures, processes and rules by which society will be governed (Mutua, 2022:7). Mutua (2022) termed this as Locke’s fraud, since the very basic principles of liberal democracy become empty vessels that can be filled with anything, unless the dialectic between norms and laws is maintained.

A couple of empirical studies of the multiparty elections of the 1990s corroborate the persistence of personalized patron-client relations in electoral politics in Africa (Lindberg, 2003; Mesfin, 2008). Perhaps this is part of a “parochial” political culture in which dependency on someone with the right political connections is prevalent (Almond, 1963; Wantchekon, 2003). Therefore, this voting behaviour provides an electoral logic that is not as much the case in other countries, where national elections are primarily about policy choices. This trend has seen proliferation of political parties and the difficulty of uniting the opposition in standing against the government party during elections (Aywa, 2015).

Political parties in Africa are often personal vehicles pursuing clientelist platforms (Wantchekon, 2003). This can be observed in the Kenyan situation where political parties rose from 6 in 1992 election to 90 the 2022 elections (Office of the Registrar of Political Parties, 2022). The number of independent candidates rose significantly and a record number were elected in various positions. This emphasizes person over party and has resulted in a prevalence in African countries of political parties that are one-person operations, which can explain why autocrats

manage to stay in power, even after elections (Baker, 1998:115). Studies by Afrobarometer (2022), which is in line with that of Bratton and Bhoojedor (2019), found that voting and popular faith in elections get a boost if citizens believe that their elections are high-quality and effective tools for holding leaders accountable.

The Afrobarometer (2022) survey about the believe in elections shows that Kenyans is among the top countries confident that elections present a chance to change leaders who are not performing. However, this confidence appears to be reducing from the 81% in the 2011/2013 survey to 75% in the 2019/2020. Support for multiparty politics rose 10 percentage points to 71% in the same period, compared to African average of 50%. Only 63% of the respondents thought the recent elections were free and fair, compared the African average of 64%, with 34% saying the results announced were inaccurate, way above African average of 26%, which is still high.

Electoral System in Kenya

In a briefing and submission to the Building Bridges to Unity and Advisory Taskforce (BBI) on 7th May 2019, Independent Electoral and Boundaries Commission (IEBC) made several suggestions for electoral reforms. In their view, the root cause of the highly divisive nature of Kenyan elections is the First-past-the-post (FPTP) electoral system inherited from colonialists (Wall, 2020). It leads to personality-based and ethnically charged elections, hence a breakdown to Kenya's social fabric. The IEBC pointed out that FPTP system was predominantly used globally, with 54% of independent states and semi-autonomous which have direct parliamentary elections use plurality-majority systems. Another 35% use Proportional Representatives (PR)-type system with the remaining 10% use semi-PR system and the rest use parallel system (The Electoral Knowledge Network, n.d.). The IEBC therefore suggested adoption of Proportional Representatives (PR) and Mixed Member Representative (MMR) models as they are more inclusive and result in fair representation. Article 81 of the Constitution requires that not more than two-thirds of the members of elective bodies should be of the same gender. Article 27 requires legislative and other measures to be taken to facilitate this two-thirds gender rule. PR and MMR models will cure the shortcomings of FPTP system to achieve more inclusive and representative electoral system (Wall, 2020). The BBI never came to fruition and hence these suggestions are yet to be implemented.

Technology is gradually shaping election experience in Kenya. Somaliland, the semi-autonomous region of Somalia, was the first country to adopt biometric identification – using iris recognition – and followed by electronic voting. Coming from warzone to having credible electoral process and systems elevated the country to limelight. Kenya adopted technology in 2022 using a specially designed Kenya Integrated Elections Management System (KIEMS). Ghana, Nigeria, South Africa and many other African countries have adopted technology, with immense benefits as to reduction of rigging, result disputation and resultant violence.

Voting and legal framework

The Constitution provides for the application of the general rules of international law (or customary international law)⁴. Among these is the 1966 International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), which is now widely recognised as laying down the following critical elements for periodic and genuine elections (also referred to as the global norm of participation)⁵. Elections must be periodic, genuine, providing the right to contest, right to vote, secret vote, universal suffrage, equal suffrage and free expression of voters' will (NEEDS/European Commission, 2007).

The 1981 African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (ACHPR) and the 2007 African Charter on Democracy, Elections and Governance (ACDEG) are also notable in the context of Africa⁶. These international conventions, amongst others, complement the Kenyan laws in guiding the conduct of the elections. IEBC carried out their exercises in accordance with the Constitution, the IEBC Act, the Elections Act, 2011, the Political Parties Act, 2011⁷ amongst other supporting laws. These include the Assumption of the Office of the President Act, No. 12 of 2012, which provides for procedure on how the person elected as

⁴ Constitution of Kenya 2010, Article 2(5) states that 'The general rules of international law shall form part of the law of Kenya'; while Article 2(6) states that 'Any treaty or convention ratified by Kenya shall form part of the law of Kenya under this Constitution.'

⁵ Article 25 of the ICCPR.

⁶ Articles 17–26 are particularly significant since they require the strengthening of electoral institutions, guarantee access to AU observer missions, and outlaw unconstitutional changes of government (e.g. *coups d'état*).

⁷ Revised in 2022 to amend s.10 to have a coalition party.

President and Deputy President, will assume office and the Publication of Electoral Opinion Polls Act, 2011, regulates the manner in which electoral opinion polls are published. The IEBC Act and the Elections Act mandates IEBC to set subsidiary legislation to enable smooth conduct of elections. The IEBC did promulgate the Elections (Registration of Voters) Regulations, 2012, and the Elections (General) Regulations, 2012.

Actions of the IEBC are subject to judicial review, unlike is some countries, like Tanzania, where the Constitution states that, ‘when a candidate is declared by the Electoral Commission to have been duly elected in accordance with this Article, then no court of law shall have any jurisdiction to inquire into the election of that candidate.’⁸ Judicial review will help nurture the fragile democracies in Africa.

The Presidential Election

In accordance with Article 132 of the Constitution, the President is elected by registered voters in a national election conducted in accordance with the Constitution and any Act of Parliament regulating presidential elections. Article 136(2) of the Constitution further specifies that it is held on the second Tuesday of August of every fifth year and held on the same day as a general election of the Members of Parliament. This helps to avoid politicians changing goalposts on election calendar.

The preparation of the elections may have been interfered with by numerous court cases, some critical ones coming as late as one day to the voting exercises. An example was on whether to stick to electronic voter identification, preferred by Ruto’s party, or resort to manual register, preferred by Raila’s party and IEBC promised to adhere to it (The Star, 2022). Ruto’s party successfully appealed, and the Court of Appeal issued a stay order just a day to the elections (Walter, 2022)⁹.

Announcement of the presidential results

The flow of the election forms is as shown in the diagram here:

⁸ Article 41(7) of the Constitution of the United Republic of Tanzania, 1977, as revised.

⁹ Stay order issued in Nairobi High Court in the Constitutional Petition E306 of 2022.

Source: IEBC

The process of at the national tallying centre is shown here:

Source: IEBC

The flow of forms in the presidential vote is shown here:

Source: IEBC

The Election Results

The 2022 presidential election was the hardest fought, resulting in the narrowest winner-loser gap in Kenya's electoral history. The IEBC announced William Ruto of Kenya Kwanza coalition party as the president-elect on August 15, 2022, after the general elections held on the August 9, 2022, and proceeded to gazette him, as per the requirements of the law. The IEBC report indicated that 14,213,027 out of 22,120,458 registered voters cast their votes, with Ruto clinching a first-round win, garnering 7,176,141 (50.49 per cent) of the votes cast and securing at least 25 per cent of the votes in 39 out of 47 counties, with Raila garnering 6,942,930 votes (48.85 per cent) (Kagwanja, 2022). Mr Odinga rejected the results as "null and void" and challenged them in the Supreme Court but the court dismissed the allegations as 'nothing more than hot air'.

#GE2022

**DECLARATION OF RESULTS FOR THE ELECTION OF PRESIDENT
OF THE REPUBLIC OF KENYA AT THE NATIONAL TALLYING CENTRE**

No.	Name of Candidates	Valid Votes in Figures	Percentage of Vote Cast	Number of counties the Candidates has attained at least 25% of Total Valid Votes Cast
1	Odinga Raila	6,942,930	48.85%	34
2	Ruto William Samoei	7,176,141	50.49%	39
3	Waihiga David Mwaure	31,987	0.23%	0
4	Wajackoyah George Luchiri	61,969	0.44%	0

<https://bit.ly/IEBC2022RESULTS>

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Core values
Adherence to the rule of law | Inclusivity | Integrity | Accountability | Teamwork | Innovativeness

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"To conduct transparent, efficient, and impartial elections; and undertake boundary delimitation for equitable representation and sustainable democracy."

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Source: IEBC

Article 138 of the Constitution vests the powers of the national returning officer to the Chairman of the IEBC. His role is to tally, verify and announce the results of vote. IEBC had set up a national tallying centre at Bomas of Kenya, Nairobi. The forms 34A and 34B were being uploaded online to the IEBC portal, and anyone with resources could download and tally. Media houses went fast and were streaming results as they come but given the differing speeds and the constituencies they started, the results were having huge variations, something that cause anxiety and confusion. Meanwhile, the commissioners were taking turns in announcing the verified results from the 291 constituencies. On 15 August 2022, hours after the planned time, the Chairman, accompanied by two other commissioners announced the results, after police quelled fracas by Azimio team who had demanded to see the results first.

Concurrently, four IEBC commissioners were holding a parallel press conference, distancing themselves from the results being

announced as ‘opaque’. Some observers pointed out that since there are seven commissioners, and four had rejected the results, the issue of quorum could be a contentious issue in the validity of the pronouncement and declaration of William Ruto as the President-elect. But as noted in the Supreme Court ruling, IEBC became dysfunctional just before announcement of the final results, yet the commissioners distancing themselves from the final tally had participated in the entire process.

The split in the commission when announcing the results may be an indication of freedom and independence to make a decision. However, further scrutiny shows that the four commissioners only joined the commission in August 2021, one year to the elections, pointing at lack of experience in handling elections, and little understanding of the role of the IEBC when it comes to results (Capital FM, 2022). It is also suspicious that their first presser outside the tallying centre, coincided with the Azimio-allied team’s exit from the tallying centre, after causing chaos. The second press release also coincided with the Azimio’s presidential candidate’s press conference rejecting the results, appearing to be reading from the same script, well-choreographed, and verbatim. This reinforced suspicion that they were brought for a mission to ensure the President’s preferred candidate wins.

The Constitution provides an avenue to challenge the outcome of the presidential election within 7 days of the announcement of the results¹⁰. By the deadline of 22nd September 2022, 9 petitions had been filed with the Supreme Court of Kenya. These were later consolidated into one petition and nine issues framed for determination¹¹. The outcome of this was issued on 5th September 2022, and it affirmed the election and announcement of William Ruto as the fifth President of Kenya. This paved way for inauguration after seven days, that happened on 13th September 2022.

Statements by Observer Missions

International election observer missions applauded the peace experience during election and the transparency IEBC exhibited but pointed out to the failure of KIEMS kits, low voter turnout, lack of youth participation and using of state resources during campaigns as the main failures during

¹⁰ Article 140(1) of the Constitution

¹¹ Presidential Election Petition No.E005 of 2022 (Consolidated with) P.E.P No.E001-E004 and P.E.P No.E007-E008 of 2022.

the August 9 General Election (Kimutai, 2022). The East Africa Community (EAC) (EAC, 2022), the Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD) (IGAD, 2022), the Commonwealth, the African Union (AU), and the Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA) observer missions released a joint statement on August 11 (AU, 2022). The European Union observer mission also issued their report, which generally reflected what other observers had in their reports (EU, 2022).

Even though the conduct of the elections was largely peaceful, there were isolated incidents of violence reported, including the national tallying centre (Daily News, 2022). IEBC returning officer for Embakasi East constituency in Nairobi, was kidnapped later found murdered with IEBC official in Mandera county shot and his leg had to be amputated. After the presidential results were announced, acts of violence by youth was reported in some parts of the country but cooled shortly after. The media was largely seen as impartial and gave critical updates to the population. Social media platforms, even though accused of misinforming the public, was equally praised for causing positive behaviour of the Electoral Management Body (EMB) due to constant monitoring and sharing of information.

The 2022 General Election in Kenya, lauded by international observers as largely peaceful and “above average”, had the lowest voter turnout in 15 years, with only 65% (14,213,027) of the 22.1 million registered voters voting (Anami, 2022). In the 2013 elections in which President Uhuru Kenyatta won, 12,330,028 registered voters voted, representing 85.91% and in the 2017 General Election, 15,593,050 registered voters representing 79.51%, turned up to cast their votes (Khaemba , 2022). The observers attributed this huge drop to lack of voter education, low interest by the youth, reduced trust and confidence in the political system, poverty and youth unemployment (Anami, 2022). Nyabola (2022) opined that voters were left in a bind. Do you vote for Odinga, the man who promises to continue the misguided policies of the last 10 years as part of his pact of continuity with Kenyatta, or for Ruto, the man who co-designed and co-championed them? (Nyabola, 2022) Almost 8 million or just over one-third of eligible voters—many of them younger than 30—decided that they preferred neither and stayed home. For Kenya, a 65 percent turnout is low.

The position of ethics in elections is remote since outsiders are obsessed with peace as the sole metric of a successful election in Africa, leaving little meaningful room to parse who the politicians are (Nyabola,

2022). In his view, the elected leaders in 2022 leaves a lot to be desired, right from the top, ranging from convicted economic saboteurs, money launderers, convicted murderers and land grabbers. 12 legislators are facing criminal court case and over 70 are facing investigations (Wangui, 2022).

Best practices and mechanisms to scale up for Africa

Best practice one: Technology. The Kenya election brought up fundamental issues for consideration such as improvement of transparency occasioned through the use of technology, and the deepening of democratic tenets among Kenyans. Technology assisted in deepening electoral transparency, enhances free and fair elections and reduces possibility of rigging. Violence usually emanates from lack of trust in the electoral processes. The transmission of results was timely and transparent, eliminating suspicion witnessed in prior elections.

Best practice two: Behavioural change. The behavioural change observed from the people at large and the institutions concerned made it clear that incumbency is no longer an iron ceiling that is impossible to crack. Kenya witnessed smooth transition after the contest, a sign of maturity in a democracy. The Kenya election has shown that the voters wield the ultimate power, being well-informed, enlightened, and ready to defend their votes. Mr Kenyatta did not sway even his voting constituency to vote for his preferred candidate, but gracefully accepted the result after the Supreme Court determination. Africans are beginning to jettison personality politics, with more focus on issues affecting their lives, like insecurity, economy and corruption, and hence people are more likely to vote on their conviction on how the candidate is expected to tackle the issues instead of the cult of personality, ethnic and religious orientation.

Best practice three: independence of judiciary, police officers and legal network. Building institutions to support elections is bearing fruits. The confidence in judiciary improved, especially after the Supreme Court annulled the 2017 election, creating an alternative avenue to seek justice to the loser (Wangui, 2022). The judges have demonstrated independence and whereas they are officially appointed by the President, he is not involved in the process of choosing them.

Even though litigation option is healthy, the bill of costs is deterrent and also serves to make the elections costly as legal fees take a huge chunk of

the IEBC budget, making Kenya elections' cost per voter the highest in the region, benefit of which goes to the lawyers (Msekwa, 2022). With each side having an array of costly senior advocates, the total cost of the 2022 presidential petition could hit a whopping 520 million Kenya Shillings (Msekwa, 2022).

Police were also better organised and more visible on the ground, with early warning signals in place. No form of harassment of opposition was witnessed and all political meetings received the same security coverage, with officers demonstrating impartiality. This is a marked contrast to the past where security officers used excessive force that caused several deaths in 2007/8 (Government of Kenya, 2008).

Best Practice four: Access to information. Kenyans continued to enjoy sharing information via mainstream media and social media unabated. It has been a trend in many African countries to restrict social media access around elections period. Restriction serves only to escalate fears and breeds mistrust and hence violence. Free media upheld transparency and helped contain irresponsible utterances of politicians, and instead, discussion focused on issues. Pollsters operated freely too. This shows that information and transparency, brings positive impact and demonstrates credibility of the elections.

Best practice five: EMBs. The selection of commissioners is well laid in the legislation, with clear timelines and activities. Kenya's Elections Act provides for out-of-country voting, one of its kind in Africa. However, the diaspora voters only participated in the presidential elections only. So far, only twelve countries have been chosen based on the number of Kenyans living there. Kenyans in diaspora have enormous contribution to the economy and foreign image of the country and deserve to have a say in the political leadership of their country. In prior elections, the only option was to travel home to register and later to vote.

Conclusion

The main objective of this paper was to examine the 2022 Kenya's election and to identify the best practices as lessons for democratization of the entire continent of Africa. It explored the democratisation progress in Africa and in Kenya, hence the electoral processes and experience of the 2022 presidential election. Kenya's election has demonstrated that democracy is thriving in Africa. It was largely

peaceful, yet highly contested. This may be attributed to structures in place to address the issues experienced from the past elections, shaped by the Supreme Court rulings over time.

Observers always reported that the election process was fair. Msekwa (2022) argued that “it is not the voting exercise that is democracy; but rather, the counting and tallying of the votes thereof” (Msekwa, 2022:7). This is an area to strengthen to demonstrate credibility of the entire exercise, and technology used should provide such assurance. Kenyan judiciary proved itself capable of exercising independent judgement and bringing finality to elections. It is the hope that free and fair elections produce desired outcomes; that political leaders will address issues bedevilling the society, which include poverty, illiteracy, hunger, unemployment, limited enlightenment and cost of living. From the lessons learnt, democratic values will entrench and become cultural reality of Africa’s future, the more the elections are held.

The Kenyan election experience has proven the Lindberg’s theoretical argument —those repetitive elections, even when flawed, are one of the important causal factors for democratization. It also upholds Rustow (1970)’s argument that democratic behaviour produces democratic values and not vice versa. The recent trend in Kenya has demonstrated a steady improvement in democratisation. However, there is still a lot of improvements to be made, if this trend is to be sustained and improve democracy ranking. African countries should build on the achievements made during the Kenyan elections. They should reform electoral process to deliver free, fair and credible elections. That will in turn deepen democracy, sustain political transformation trend, hence prosperity and good hope for Africa and its people.

Recommendation for improvement

Public communication: The transparency surpassed expectations, but EMB should however manage public expectations and improve stakeholder relations with robust public communication strategies.

Preparation: due to failure in technology, inadequate voter education and inadequate resources, EMB should improve on preparation and resource allocation. IEBC should consider doing mock elections before the real elections, to test their systems and possible scenarios to avoid hiccups witnessed in many polling stations. They should consider

adequate training of officials doing the tallying and casting is needed is necessary to avoid court reprisals¹².

Post-election review: They were repeated errors, going by the petitions lodged after the last five elections. A proper review of all processes should be conducted after every election to continuously improve, with notable challenges acted upon, including amendments to requisite laws to smoothen the operations during elections.

Voter registration: EMBs should maintain accurate, credible and accessible national voters' registers and ensure continuous updating of the roll, and involvement of political parties to improve transparency and eliminate suspicion of fraud. Better budget allocation to enable continuous voters' registration, and even be done alongside issuance of national identity cards.

EMB Independence and impartiality: The selection of commissioners should be through a transparent and inclusive process. EMB should have independent sources of funds, as opposed to relying on the executive to release funds to them. Administrative and managerial autonomy of EMBs should be secured to enable them to perform their duties effectively and avoid reliance on government officials or interference from them in the course of discharging their duties.

Commissioner's roles and tenure: There was evidence of interference of secretariat by commissioners, by assuming administrative duties. Perhaps an amendment to Section 5 of the IEBC Act to make the commissioners part-time instead of being full-time and to delineate their duties and roles, retaining governance and leaving administrative duties to the secretariat. The commissioners' tenure is six years non-renewable. But where they are appointed at the same time, the exit at the same time, leaving no institutional memory. Their tenures should be scattered, and during selection, deputy Chair should hold same qualification as the Chair and hence seamlessly assume the role of the Chair should there be a vacancy. IEBC Chair is required to hold qualifications equivalent to the High Court judge, but his deputy did not hold any legal qualification.

¹² The Malawi presidential election was nullified on account of many erasures using correction fluid and overwritten.

Voter education: There is voter apathy, looking at the trend in the last three elections. EMB should ensure citizenry understand country's democracy and how to participate in it, including by voting. EMB should forge partnerships with civil society and other civic education providers with a common curriculum. This will address what observers lack of voter education, low interest by the youth, reduced trust and confidence in the political system, poverty and youth unemployment (Anami, 2022).

Dispute resolution: Electoral disputes are unavoidable but EMBs may be empowered to resolve lower-level disputes, but also make provision for courts of law to be the final arbiters, with clear timelines. EMBs should have the power to ensure that the political parties competing in elections respect electoral laws, comply with registration requirements and adhere to campaign finance rules and codes of conduct.

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